

Production of hydrochar fuel by microwave-hydrothermal carbonisation of olive pomace slurry from olive oil industry for combustion application

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Abbreviations

OP = Olive Pomace; Sample ID of 180-2 means hydrochar produced at 180 °C for 2 min holding time, similar meaning applied to 180-16, 180-30, 215-2, 215-16, 215-30, 250-2, 250-16, and 250-30.

Table S1. Operational conditions assayed for MHTC of wet olive pomace.

Sample ID	T_R (°C)		t_R (min)	
	Coded	Real	Coded	Real
180-2	- 1	180	- 1	2
180-16	- 1	180	0	16
180-30	- 1	180	+ 1	30
215-2	0	215	- 1	2
215-16	0	215	0	16
215-16	0	215	0	16
215-16	0	215	0	16
215-30	0	215	+ 1	30
250-2	+ 1	250	- 1	2
250-16	+ 1	250	0	16
250-30	+ 1	250	+ 1	30

Note: T_R = reaction temperature; t_R = reaction time (holding time at T_R).

Table S2. Structural composition of raw material and hydrochars (produced at different severity factors).

Sample ID	Severity Factor (logR₀)	Holocellulose %	Acid-insoluble Lignin %	Extractives %
OP		37.53	36.82	11.50
180-2	3.050	30.85	46.52	17.62
180-16	3.633	24.07	48.51	18.07
180-30	3.874	25.00	46.17	17.75
215-2	4.015	7.63	57.70	19.15
215-16	4.647	6.50	59.69	19.37
215-30	4.895	3.98	59.97	23.97
250-2	5.071	6.25	59.53	20.35
250-16	5.684	2.06	61.88	23.75
250-30	5.929	2.96	64.30	22.52

Note: T_R = reaction temperature; t_R = reaction time (holding time at T_R);

Table S3. Mineral composition (mean values in %) of raw material and hydrochars.

Sample ID	Na₂O	MgO	Al₂O₃	SiO₂	P₂O₅	K₂O	CaO	TiO₂	Fe₂O₃
OP	0.28	0.15	0.06	0.12	0.18	2.41	0.64	0.0011	0.11
180-2	1.17	0.16	0.04	0.27	0.14	0.67	0.93	0.0005	0.03
180-16	1.50	0.18	0.05	0.28	0.13	0.76	0.99	0.0006	0.03
180-30	0.96	0.17	0.05	0.27	0.13	0.83	0.99	0.0005	0.03
215-2	0.17	0.05	0.04	0.10	0.10	0.60	0.59	0.0005	0.03
215-16	0.67	0.13	0.06	0.31	0.05	0.40	0.96	0.0015	0.04
215-30	0.70	0.16	0.05	0.25	0.18	0.47	1.20	0.0007	0.03
250-2	1.15	0.16	0.07	0.32	0.11	0.26	1.01	0.0013	0.05
250-16	0.34	0.14	0.09	0.33	0.19	0.30	1.08	0.0017	0.04
250-30	0.19	0.14	0.08	0.33	0.28	0.27	1.03	0.0032	0.05

Conversion factors information used to convert elements into minerals are available on <https://www.jcu.edu.au/advanced-analytical-centre/resources/element-to-stoichiometric-oxide-conversion-factors>.

Figure S1. FTIR spectra of raw material and hydrochars.

Figure S2. Moisture sorption by raw material and hydrochars.

Figure S3. Observed versus predicted plots for: (a) hydrochar yield, %; (b) equilibrium moisture content, mg/g; (c) higher heating value, MJ/kg; (d) lower heating value, MJ/kg. White points correspond to assays carried out at center point of domain.

Figure S4. Coefficient plots (scaled and centered) for the models corresponding to: (a) hydrochar yield, %; (b) moisture sorption capacity, mg/g; (c) higher heating value, MJ/kg; and (d) lower heating value, MJ/kg.